

Additional replicate data for manuscript: **A surface-exposed cardiolipin synthase provides a new paradigm in maintaining the Gram-negative outer membrane**

Authors: Herrera, Ellison, and Trent

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Figure 2 replicate (R) data

Figure 2A

Figure 2B

EV: empty vector

Figure 2C

Figure 3 replicate data

Figure 3B

Figure 3C

Figure 3B

Figure 3C

Figure 4 replicate data

Figure 4B

His-tagged pull down

Biotin detection

R2

Figure 4C

Figure 4C

Figure 5 replicate data

Figure 5A

Whole cells dot blot

R2

R3

Western blots

R2

R3

Figure 5B

WC = Whole-cells; PL = Pre-lysed. T1&T2: Technical repetitions. R1 & R2: Biological repetitions, no adjustment on birghtness/contrast

Figure 6 replicate data

Figure 6

Figure 7 replicate data

Figure 7B

A. baumannii Δ *clsCOD*, membrane fractions

Figure 7C

Figure 8 replicate data

Figure 9 replicate data

Figure 9B

Figure S4 replicate data

Figure S4

Figure S5 replicate data

Figure S5

Figure S5

R2

E. coli
 Δ *clsABC*

E. coli
 Δ *clsABC*

EV

Clso
ClsO-His₈

Figure S6 replicate data

Figure S6A

Figure S6B

Figure S6C

Figure S7 replicate data

Figure S7B

Figure S8 replicate data

Figure S8A

A. baumannii
19606

Figure S8B

R2

A. baumannii
19606

